

Request For Information Submission

Submitting Organization: Information Technology Systems Center at the University of Alabama in Huntsville (ITSC UAH)

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Digital Object Identifier:

The Information Technology and Systems Center (ITSC) conducts multidisciplinary research at the University of Alabama in Huntsville (UAH) in many facets of information technology. Basic and applied research is performed to develop new techniques and systems that solve real-world problems by the transfer of innovative technologies and knowledge. Students, faculty and research scientists are involved in all aspects of the center. ITSC serves as the focal point for UAH research endeavors in information technology and systems and provides leadership in applications of information technology for multiple disciplines and computational environments.

ITSC manages the Global Hydrometeorology Resource Center Distributed Active Archive Center (GHRC DAAC), a joint effort with the National Aeronautics and Space Administration's Marshall Space Flight Center (NASA MSFC). GHRC DAAC provides a comprehensive archive of data and knowledge augmentation services with a focus on hazardous weather, its governing dynamical and physical processes, and associated applications. GHRC focuses on lightning, tropical cyclones and storm-induced hazards through integrated collections of satellite, airborne, and in-situ data sets. GHRC is a member of the World Data System and is Core Trust Seal certified, demonstrating that GHRC attains a high level of trustworthy data structures.

ITSC focuses on real-world applications emphasizing open source solutions using cloud-based, serverless technologies with machine learning and artificial intelligence techniques. This real-world effort demonstrates ITSC's user services focus and ITSC aims for modular tools and open source capabilities. A number of activities highlight our organization's capabilities to promote open science, directly addressing the Earth System Observatory's needs. GHRC is the pathfinder for all of NASA's Distributed Active Archive Centers (DAACs) in transitioning to a cloud-based DAAC. This has provided ITSC/GHRC personnel a wealth of experience in performing data management with open source cloud activities.

ITSC/GHRC personnel also are producing a number of activities to enable users to visualize, process, and analyze data in an open source format. This includes the Cloud-based Analytic Framework for Precipitation Research ([CAPri](#)) to conduct precipitation analyses and enhance the Global Precipitation Mission's spatial resolution. The Field Campaign eXplorer ([FCX](#)) provides a data exploration, visualization, and analysis capabilities for a variety of datasets in a coincident display. FCX is further capable of being extended by users generating their own Application Programming Interfaces (APIs). Additionally, new features such as Earthdata Pub and Bulk Downloader are systems to improve data management to streamline data ingest and data egress, respectively. These efforts utilize a wide array of data types and volumes, demonstrating ITSC's capabilities in managing and using big data.

ITSC's abilities span end-to-end user applications. These promote community goals of FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) and TRUST (Transparency, Responsibility, User Focus, Sustainability, and Technology). Combined, ITSC supports data management, exploration, egress, visualization, and analysis.

Response to Subject #2, Open Science:

Open science is a “*collaborative culture enabled by technology that empowers the open sharing of data, information, and knowledge within the scientific community and the wider public to accelerate scientific research and understanding.*” Following the principles of FAIR and TRUST, this requires free access to data, metadata, and tools that can be used for various research applications. In order for this to be achieved, new missions must establish a data management plan, including workflows, that describe end-to-end processes with which all relevant data are handled. This ranges from ingest to the final visualizations and analyses.

Missions require a full understanding of where data will come from and how it will be stored, analyzed, displayed, and accessed by the user community. NASA’s DAACs address this process for NASA Earth observing data. ITSC manages the GHRC DAAC and through internal activities and collaboration, has developed a data management system that provides an end-to-end workflow. Each of these capabilities now utilized cloud-based, serverless technologies with open source capabilities. Collaboratively, the DAAC is preparing the release of Earthdata Pub. This enterprise-level tool is designed to provide a single interface for data providers to send data to the DAACs. Missions will need the capability to manage and direct the inflow of Earth observation data, which Earthdata Pub can serve as an example.

Data visualization and analysis is another component that new missions need. ITSC/GHRC have established two systems to address this. As previously mentioned, these are FCX and CAPRi. FCX is a cloud-native system that has been designed to visualize multiple datasets. Particularly, these datasets can be from different platforms (e.g., ground-, airborne-, and satellite-based) and can range from point observations to three-dimensional volumes. FCX has required the development of various techniques to coincidentally visualize these disparate datasets, both temporally and spatially. This includes the use of Cesium to dynamically display data as the display zooms in and out to effectively use memory resources. Furthermore, as a cloud-native system, FCX does not require users to download the system to use. Additionally, as an open source system FCX enables users outside of ITSC/GHRC to develop their own APIs to view and analyze data. This capability is a vital component to future missions. This capability allows users to extend research beyond the science team’s initial efforts.

Like FCX, the CAPRi system is a separate cloud-based visualization and display system. CAPRi has been designed to perform intercomparison analyses between different styles of data focusing on similar observational parameters. This CAPRi ability highlights the importance of having varied techniques to analyze core mission data, but also enable its use with supporting datasets that were not part of the initial mission.

Lastly, missions require a methodology in the data management plan to allow access to the data for the user community. The FCX and Bulk Downloader tools, created by ITSC/GHRC are an example of this final step in data management. FCX includes components allowing users to access supporting documentation, metadata, and data Digital Object Identifiers. A three-dimensional data subsetter further allows users to select a three-dimensional volume to obtain all data in that volume. Bulk Downloader interfaces with NASA’s Earthdata Search to rapidly access large volumes of data. Overall, future missions require a plan that enables data management, visualization and analysis, and data egress. Focusing on cloud-based, open source systems expand access to the community and enable extension of capabilities by the user community.

Links to Relevant Activities

Below are links to the various projects, described above, along with supporting documentation, where appropriate.

Field Campaign eXplorer (FCX)

- <https://ghrc.earthdata.nasa.gov/fcx/index.html> (open source release April 2022)
- Stano, G. T., Y. Wu, N. R. Selvaraj, M. Maskey and A. Kulkarni, "The Field Campaign Explorer," *2021 IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium IGARSS*, 2021, pp. 3257-3260, doi: 10.1109/IGARSS47720.2021.9553677.

Earthdata Pub

- Ellington, B., E. Campos, W. Ellett, T. Wright, D. Wright, K. Broughton, T. Walker, M. Maskey, and G. Stano, "Earthdata Pub: An Enterprise-Wide Solution to Submit Data to NASA's Distributed Active Archive Centers," submitted to *2022 IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium IGARSS, 2022*, https://ghrc.nsstc.nasa.gov/home/sites/default/files/EarthdataPub_IGARSS_2022.pdf.

Cloud-based Analytic Framework for Precipitation Research (CAPRI)

- <https://agu.confex.com/agu/fm21/meetingapp.cgi/Paper/838657>